

Flexible free-standing composite films including skeleton-structures of hollow graphene ellipsoids

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Introduction

Why 3D interconnected framework ?

Strategy

Fabrication of conductive hybrid with lower loading of filler through

1. conductive pathway imparted by 3-D interconnected framework, and
2. few layer graphene nanosheets (GNS) with less amount of defects

Objectives

Shape-control for conduction control

- ✓ Tailored assembly of non-spherical particles
- Non-spherical NPs with tailored assembly for effective conduction pathway with suppression of strayed electron transport
- Lesser amount of hybrid particles for design flexibility

Experimental

Mechanical milling of graphite to size-controlled GNS

3D Framework of GNS

Results and Discussion

Fabrication of PS Ellipsoids by Mechano-thermal Elongation

3D Framework of GNS by mixing with Ellipsoid Assembly

Electrical conductivity of 3D Framework based on Spheroids

Electrical conductivity of 3D Framework based on Ellipsoids

Conductivity Changes under Deformation

Excellent deformability of the composite film of PVA and GNS framework

- The GNS ellipsoid assembly-based 3-D framework exhibited **lower resistance change** than the typical spheroid-based case.
- 3D framework with higher amount of GNS showed less change of resistance under mechanical deformation.

Conclusion

Tailored 3D framework-embedded composite

- Tailored 3D framework architectures possess porous structure with efficient electron transfer pathway
- Simple and cost-effective.
- Capable of mixing with various polymers (even flexible..)

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